

The Effectiveness Of Online Learning During The Covid-19 Pandemic At Higher Education In Indonesia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 03, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 27, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Online Learning, Online Media, Writing Learning Course, Higher Education</p>	<p><i>This study aims to explore the effectiveness of online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic at Universitas Negeri Makassar, Indonesia. There were 95 students participated in this study. The students were from Indonesian Language and Literature Study Program at Faculty of Languages and Literature State University of Makassar in 2020/2021 academic year. The study therefore concludes that 1) Students are very active in communicating ideas, thoughts, and feelings in online classrooms in the outbreak of Covid-19 pandemic, 2) The flexibility of online classes is more important to students, 3) The participation rate of participants in online classes is higher than traditional classes (face to face), 4) Online classes are no problem especially those related to internet networks, 5) Students do not experience difficulties in online classes.</i></p>
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Introduction

At the end of 2020, the world was jolted by the presence of the Covid-19 pandemic which threatens human lives around the world. This threat is still ongoing today and still shows an increasing trend. Covid-19 changed all aspects of education, especially the delivery of learning (Kusumawati, 2020, p. 287). The World University Rankings as cited in Radu, et al. (2020, 2) report that in the higher education sector, universities have been forced to close their doors in response to the growing coronavirus outbreak and, where IT infrastructure allows, shift classrooms to online learning and maintain student retention and maintain access to learning.

The Covid-19 outbreak forced many schools and colleges to be temporarily closed (Dhawan, 2020, p. 6). Therefore, Dhawan added, there are several affected areas around the world and it is feared that they will be left behind during the current semester or even more in the future.

This emergency situation forces academic institutions to shift from traditional classrooms to online learning platforms and this is important as students enrolled in the institution has a predefined syllabus and time to discuss it (Shaheen& Maryam, 2020).

This condition forces all schools, universities, government offices, and even some private companies migrate to virtual or online work (work from home/WFH). Teachers at education sector try to maintain their services in education and teaching using a variety of media platforms in online learning. This reveals that the existence of the online learning in this Covid-19 pandemic becomes vital in education sector. Online learning is now reaching its core, helping to transform higher education and moving beyond isolated attempts to influence and change widely (Otte&Benke, 2006). Online learning is currently experiencing an explosive growth rate and more and more participating researchers, practitioners, and institutions are realizing reduced operating costs (Saadé, et al., 2017, p. 148). Continuous education during the Corona virus can be done through online teaching (Destianingsih&Satria, 2020, p. 152). This present study explores the potential findings of effective online learning in the outbreak of Covid-19 pandemic at the university level.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Online Learning

The era of information and technology is marked by an unprecedented rate of technological development and has become an inseparable part of our lives even in the classroom (Yaman, et al., 2015, p. 1). Online learning can be called a tool that can make the teaching-learning process more student-centered, more innovative, and even more flexible (Dhawan, 2020, p. 6). Therefore, Dhawan argues that online learning is defined as “learning

experiences in a synchronous or asynchronous environment using different devices (eg. cell phones, laptops, etc.) with internet access.

Online learning refers to a learning environment supported by the Internet (Bakia, et al., 2012). Bhakia et al then revealed that online learning consists of various programs that use the internet inside and outside the school walls to provide access to teaching materials and facilitate interaction between teachers and students. Online learning is focused not only on the online context, but also includes a variety of computer-based learning platforms and delivery methods, genres, formats and media such as multimedia, educational programming, simulations, games and the use of new media in any way, and mobile platforms in all disciplines (Keengwe& Kidd, 2010, p. 533).

Online learning is the use of the internet to access learning materials; to interact with content, instructors, and other learners; and to get support during the learning process, to acquire knowledge, to construct personal meaning, and to grow from the learning experience (Anderson & Elloumi, 2004). Online learning takes place at nearly every college and university in the country. Even traditionally taught courses routinely take advantage of online learning tools. For example, institutions capture lectures via video, archive them on the web, and make them available to students and in some cases publicly, in asynchronous format (Bacow, et al., 2012).

Previous Studies in Online Learning amidst Covid-19 Pandemic

Table 1 presents previous studies in online learning in Covid-19 pandemic. As revealed in Table 1, the researchers were from a variety of countries. The researchers conducted their research by employing a variety of instruments and the subjects or participants were vary from high school students, university students to teachers.

Table 1. The measurement of the Online Learning in Covid-19 Pandemic in previous studies

Researcher	Research Site & Year	Instrument	Subjects/Participants
I Gede Sedana Suci, et al.	Indonesia, 2021	Classroom Action Research	University students
Alena Haskova, et al	Slovak Republic, 2021	Panel discussion	Teachers
Kusumawati & Anggara Jatu	Indonesia, 2021	Questionnaire	Students
Mikhail V. Vinichenko, et al	Moscow, Russia, 2021	A questionnaire and interview	University students
Tatiana Aleksandrovna Polushkina & Elena Genrikhovna Tareva	Moscow, Russia, 2021	Interviews, rating scales and participant observation	University students
Like Raskova Octaberlina & Afif Ikhwanul Muslimin	Indonesia, 2021	Questionnaire	University students
Destianingsih & Satria	Indonesia, 2020	Questionnaire	Students
Larisa V. Ukhova, et al	Russia, 2021	Interview	University students
Aleksander Kobylarek, et al	Poland, Belarus, Italy, Ukraine and Georgia, 2021	Interview Technique	Foreign language teachers
Botagoz Suiyerkul, et al	Kazakhstan, 2020	World Bank's data on Kazakhstan	University students
Florence Orabueze, et al	Nigeria, 2021	Interview through FGD	University students
Daniel R. Bailey	South Korea, 2020	Electronic Survey	A group of 43 EFL university instructors
Irina V. Tivyaeva & Albina A. Vodyanitskaya	Moscow, Russia, 2021	Questionnaires, regular class observations, student self-assessment reports, open discussions and retrospective protocols.	University students
Rana Hasan Kandeel	Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA), 2021	Two mediums of direct observation and the open questionnaire	University students

RehamAlkhudiry&Ameen Alahdal	Saudi Arabia, 2021	Motivation Inventory (IMI) scale	120 undergraduate students
Ekaterina A. Samorodova, et al	Russia, 2021	Observation	University students
Bambang AgusDarwant,	Indonesia, 2021	Surveys and focus group discussions	University teachers
TolganayKurmanbayeva, et al	Kazakhstan, 2021	Reading & oral communication	University students
Darya Viktorovna Aleynikova	Russia, 2021	Test	University students
Monica Ortiz, et al	Spain, 2021	Ethnography	Immigrant students
Oksana Hrydzhuk, et al	Ukraine, 2021	Online assessment of learning outcomes	University students
Vera Levina, et al	Russia, 2021	The axiological phraseology tasks	A total of 260 university students
AriadnaStrugielska, et al	Poland, 2021	Survey questions	Polish language teachers
Marina R. Zheltukhina,	Russia, 2021	Home reading lessons	Secondary school students
Siti Sarah Fitriani, et al	Indonesia, 2021	Online discussions	Undergraduate students
AisuluNurtayeva, et al	Kazakhstan, 2021	Interviews and observations	Twenty-two philology students

Effectiveness of Online Learning

Effective online learning requires interdependence for shared understanding of learning objectives in the learning community (Vonderwell & Zachariah, 2005). [Neuhauser](#) (2010) says that ninety-six percent of online students think this course is effective or more effective for their learning than face-to-face courses in general.

Zerr (2007) argues that there is a high level of satisfaction with class attendance systems, and in particular with regard to the usefulness of online homework in helping students understand the concepts of first semester calculus. Benbunan-Fich, R & Hiltz, S. R. (2003) state online course outcomes improve when professors structure them to support the growth of the learning community, by being available online for interaction with students, and by using collaborative learning strategies.

Smart & Cappel (2006) say that participants in the elective courses rated the online module significantly better compared to compulsory courses. Overall, participants in the elective courses rated the online module as slightly positive while those who took the compulsory courses rated it slightly negatively.

Smart & Cappel (2006) therefore argue that their study entitled “Students’ Perceptions of Online Learning: A Comparative Study” provide provides guidance on how online components and strategies can be applied to enhance teaching and learning in the 21st century, particularly as we work to actively engage students in learning, to provide real-world contexts for learning, and to promote critical thinking and deep learning.

According to Shaheen and Maryam (2020) in their study conclude that in general, the transition from traditional classrooms to online education systems is growing quite fruitful.

RESEARCH METHOD

Investigative site and participants

There were 95 participants in this study, 83 or 87.37% women and 12 or 12.63%. The participants were the students of Indonesian Language and Literature Study Program, Faculty of Languages and Literature State University of Makassar, Indonesia. This present study used a close ended questionnaire to obtain data from participants. To obtain the data, the questionnaire was distributed to participants on February 2021.

Instrument, material, and procedure

The instrument of the study was questionnaire consisting of demographic participants such as gender, age, semester, ethnic group, and statements containing questions related to the effectiveness of online learning using online media in the Covid-19 pandemic online learning consisting of 26 statements. In this present study, the participants were asked to rate their perceptions with response to test the effectiveness of online learning using online media in online learning under the Covid-19 pandemic on a 5-point scale (Strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and disagree). Data were coded and analysed using percentage, table, and graphic and followed by interpretation and explanation by relating with the previous related studies.

Data analysis

Data analysis uses SPSS by displaying percentages, tables and graphs so that there is an explanation, interpretation and presentation of supporting data from previous related research. This descriptive statistic (percentage) is calculated for responses to survey items.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results and Discussion

There were 12 (12.63%) of the participants were male and 83 (87.37%) were female as revealed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Gender of Participants

Figure 2 presents the age distribution of the sample used for analysis. 15 or 15.79% of the participants were age of 18. 44 or 46.31% of the participants were age of 19. 20 or 21.05% of the participants were age of 20. 11 or 11.58% of the participants were 21, and 5 or 5.26% of the participants were age of 22.

Figure 2. Age of Participants

Figure 3. Ethnic Group of Participants

The participants were from 5 ethnic groups in Indonesia. 50 or 52.63% were from Buginese, 37 or 38.95% were from Makassarese, 5 or 5.26% were from Mandarese, 1.05 or % were from Javanese, 1 or 1.05% were from Selayarese, and 1 or 1.05% were from Flores.

The semester of participants ranging from the second to the sixth semester in 2020/2021 academic year. There were 12 or 12.63% were from the second semester. 67 or 70.53% were from the fourth semester, and 16 or 16.84% were from sixth semester as revealed in Figure 3.

Figure 4. Semester of Participants

Descriptive Statistics of Participants' Perception in on Online Learning

Table 2. Distributions for Participants' Perception on the Effectiveness of Online Learning

Item	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
1	1.00	5.00	2.8737	.99190	.192	-.453
2	1.00	5.00	3.3474	.98681	-.208	-.074
3	2.00	5.00	3.4316	.73878	.079	-.232
4	1.00	4.00	2.3684	.70034	.104	-.136
5	2.00	5.00	3.6526	.86009	.025	-.709
6	1.00	4.00	2.4632	.74105	.770	-.099
7	1.00	5.00	3.4000	.74947	-.812	1.832
8	1.00	5.00	2.3579	.66710	.759	1.861
9	2.00	5.00	3.4737	.71224	-.086	-.215
10	1.00	4.00	2.5263	.88537	.247	-.718
11	2.00	5.00	3.3158	.67261	.169	-.015
12	1.00	4.00	2.4947	.71271	.919	-.172
13	1.00	5.00	2.9263	.81531	.498	.810
14	1.00	5.00	2.9263	.90203	.147	-.539
15	1.00	5.00	2.2947	1.45041	.964	-.456
16	1.00	5.00	4.0316	1.00480	-1.478	2.418
17	1.00	4.00	2.4842	.78365	-.285	-.390
18	2.00	5.00	3.4737	.90908	.036	-.759
19	1.00	5.00	3.3368	1.03770	-.485	-.388
20	1.00	5.00	2.6316	.82582	.089	.555
21	1.00	5.00	2.8105	.87877	-.482	.124
22	2.00	5.00	2.9263	.71818	.462	.144
23	2.00	5.00	3.5053	.66642	.751	-.195
24	1.00	5.00	2.5579	.90760	.391	-.472
25	1.00	5.00	3.5895	.85670	-.855	.761
26	1.00	5.00	2.7895	.86165	.322	.589

To illustrate the general tendency of students' perception on the effectiveness of online learning using online media in amidst of Covid-19 pandemic, it is required the determination of the mean, standard deviation, maximum, minimum, skewness, and kurtosis of the effectiveness of online learning. Descriptive statistics (min, max, mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis for students' perception are displayed in Table 2. As seen in Table 2, participants' responses ranged in five points on the scale. The results of the study shows that the participants achieved a mean of 2.8737 and SD = .99190 for student's perception number 1. The participants achieved a mean of 3.3474 and SD = .98681 for student's perception number 2. The students achieved a mean of 3.4316 and SD = .73878 for student's perception number 3. The students achieved a mean of 2.3684 and SD = .70034 for student's perception number 4. The students achieved a mean of 3.6526 and SD = .86009 for students' perception number 5. The means and Standard Deviation (SD) for students' perception number 6 to number 25 are clearly revealed on Table 2. The normal distribution can be seen for all scales in this study as reflected by skewness and kurtosis value as presented in Table 2. The item's skewness and kurtosis values are mostly in the range -1 and +1. Univariate normality is considered to be supported according to the ± 2 thresholds for the slope and kurtosis suggested by Kunnan in Peng (2013).

Table 4. Percentage of Students' Perception on the Effectiveness of Online Learning

Item	Students' Perception	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	The level of student interaction in online classes is higher than face-to-face classes.	5.3	21.1	35.8	31.6	6.3
2	The level of student interaction in online classes is lower than face-to-face classes.	12.6	29.5	42.1	11.6	4.2
3	The flexibility of online classes is more important to me.	6.3	38.9	46.3	8.4	0
4	The flexibility of online classes is not important to me	0	4.2	36.8	50.5	8.4
5	Students in online classes are actively involved in the learning process.	17.9	36.8	37.9	7.4	0
6	Students in online classes are not actively involved in the learning process	0	11.6	26.3	58.9	3.2
7	The media platform used in online learning is very reliable.	3.2	43.2	47.4	3.2	3.2
8	The media platform used in online learning is not very supportive.	1.1	2.1	33.7	57.9	5.3
9	I encountered difficulties in online classes.	5.3	44.2	43.2	7.4	0
10	I didn't find it difficult in online classes	0	16.8	28.4	45.3	9.5
11	Students are very active in communicating in online classes.	3.2	33.7	54.7	8.4	0
12	Students are very inactive in communicating in online classes.	0	11.6	27.4	60.0	1.1
13	Online class students are more enthusiastic than face-to-face classes.	5.3	11.6	55.8	25.3	2.1
14	Online class students are less enthusiastic than face-to-face classes.	3.2	24.2	37.9	31.6	3.2
15	Online classes have no problem especially related to the internet network.	17.9	2.1	9.5	32.6	37.9
16	Online classes often create problems especially related to internet networks.	33.7	48.4	10.5	2.1	5.3
17	I am more satisfied with online class attendance than face-to-face class.	0	6.3	47.4	34.7	11.6
18	I am not satisfied with online class attendance rather than face-to-face class.	13.7	34.7	36.8	14.7	0
19	I can access online classes anywhere.	9.5	42.1	26.3	16.8	5.3
20	I can't access online classes in my area.	2.1	7.4	50.5	31.6	8.4
21	My/student participation rates are higher in online classes than traditional (face-to-face) classes.	1.1	16.8	54.7	16.8	10.5
22	My/student participation rate is lower in online classes than traditional (face-to-face) classes.	2.1	15.8	54.7	55.8	1.1

23	Students use a variety of learning resources in online classes rather than face-to-face classes.	8.4	34.7	55.8	1.1	0
24	Students do not use a variety of learning resources in online classes rather than face-to-face classes.	1.1	16.8	27.4	46.3	8.4
25	Technical problems did not dampen my enthusiasm for online classes.	8.4	55.8	24.2	9.5	2.1
26	Technical problems dampen my enthusiasm for online classes.	4.2	10.5	50.5	29.5	5.3

The most frequent response of students' perception on the effectiveness of online learning is shown on Table 3. This table reveals the proportion of participants who endorsed the five options on the Likert scale (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree). As revealed in Table 3, the majority of participants expressed their responses "Disagree" on the statement: Students are very inactive in communicating in online classes (Item 12, 60.0%). This means that the students are very active in maintaining communication in online class. Detail percentage of the effectiveness of online learning using online media is displayed on Table 3.

Proportion of Participants' Response on Effectiveness of Online Learning

Figure 1 shows the proportion of participants' response on effectiveness of online learning using online media during the Covid-19 pandemic at higher education in Indonesia.

Figure 1. Proportion of Students' Response on Online Learning

Discussion

This present study was conducted to investigate the effectiveness of online learning using online media in online learning in the outbreak of Covid-19 pandemic at higher education in Indonesia. The findings of the study reveal that: Firstly, students are very active in communicating ideas, thoughts, and feeling in online classes. This finding is consistent with Khan, et al. (2017) who emphasize its importance deliberate course design in an attempt to actively engage students in the online course setting. Secondly, the flexibility of online classes is more important to students. Flexibility in class schedule and availability of instructor's positive experience were two important things in an online course. Convenience, availability of instructors, and online interaction were cited as positives (Mansour & Mupinga, 2007). Thirdly, participants' participation rates are higher in online classes than traditional (face-to-face) classes. This finding is consistent with Kim (2013) who asserts that a high quality participation in a large online class could be effected through sub-grouping. Similarly, Parks-Stamm, et al.

(2016) argue that students' participation in online class discussion is associated with positive outcomes for students' achievement and satisfaction. Thirdly, online classes have no problem especially related to the internet network. The participants' responses on the internet network during online class runs well. This give opportunity to the students learns the material well. Lastly, the students didn't find it difficult in online classes. This finding inconsistent with Ellis, et al. (2005) who assert that a significant percentage of the surveyed students adopted a poor approach to learning with online resources in mixed experiences even when their overall learning experience was related to a cohesive conception of veterinary science, and the differences were even greater marked for less successful students.

CONCLUSION

The current study concludes that 1) Students are very active in communicating ideas, thoughts, and feelings in online classrooms in the outbreak of Covid-19 pandemic, 2) The flexibility of online classes is more important to students, 3) The participation rate of participants in online classes is higher than traditional classes (face to face), 4) Online classes are no problem especially those related to internet networks, 5) Students do not experience difficulties in online classes.

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